

Music of chaos

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Music and songs express ideas and stories. Works are best understood in the contexts in which they were conceived, so art is communication because it generates dialogues among its viewers.

Recent events in Ecuador leave a soundtrack. New styles, lyrics, and chords impose themselves and feed the currents of consumption. It is understood that each generation brings forms of speech and manifest different optics. Some melodies survive and help researchers to continue on the routes of their creators.

But, perhaps today it points to a society gone astray, non-existent leaderships and the emergence of anonymous tyrants who control the country. Besides, compositions are not always written or sung by artists or groups, there are automatism in combination with statistics that replace humans.

The ideals of peace, encounter or tolerance, the themes of love or indifference, the hymns of victory or the social song are replaced by a huge production of homogeneous titles that exhibit a standard where the regularity is fatality, poverty, violence, and the abysses between the few "rich" and the marginalized.

There are also breakthroughs that get minimal exposure in the mainstream media. The standard is to circulate light singles with few reflections and easy refrains. In spite of that, there are people who break the molds to show that goodness, beauty, and aesthetics survive, but they are few.

One of the signs that Ecuadorians are moving in the direction of solving their problems will be to hear from their artists the hope that "there is light at the end of the tunnel". Music, its singers and the people do not lie and always speak the truth. Hopefully this will happen soon.